

A new species of *Alvania* (Mollusca, Rissoidae) from Annobón (Gulf of Guinea, West Africa)

Una nueva especie de *Alvania* (Mollusca, Rissoidae) de Annobón (Golfo de Guinea, África occidental)

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ABSTRACT

Alvania gascoignei spec. nov. from Annobón is described as new for science. It is compared with other species of this genus in eastern Atlantic.

RESUMEN

Se describe una especie nueva para la ciencia, *Alvania gascoignei* spec. nov., procedente de Annobón y se compara con otras del mismo género del Atlántico oriental.

KEY WORDS: *Alvania*, Rissoidae, new species, Annobón, Guinea Equatorial.

PALABRAS CLAVE: *Alvania*, Rissoidae, nueva especie, Annobón, Guinea Ecuatorial.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Alvania* Risso, 1826 is one of most numerous in species within the Rissoidae of the Eastern Atlantic. So, descriptions of species of this genus are present in a high number of publications. GOFAS AND WARÉN (1982) showed the genus in the Iberian and Moroccan coast. In the Mediterranean, this genus has been mainly studied by Italian malacologist and a compendium of colour photographs of all of them can be seen in GIANUZZI-SAVELLI, PUSATERI, PALMERI AND EBREO (1996). A recent revision of the West African species of *Alvania* was included in GOFAS (1999). In the other hand, MOOLENBEEK AND HOENSELAAR (1989) and HOENSELAAR AND GOUD (1998) dealt the genus in the eastern Atlantic archipelagos, and BOUCHET AND WARÉN (1993) studied the

bathyal and abyssal species of the northern Atlantic.

Annobón is the most southwestern island in the Gulf of Guinea, about 200 kms at southwest of São Tomé. The marine molluscan fauna of São Tomé and Príncipe has been studied by FERNANDES AND ROLÁN (1993). Few information exists on the Annobón molluscan fauna (ALVARADO AND ALVAREZ, 1964).

An unknown species of this genus was found in sediment obtained during the Annobón 2000 Expedition and is described in the present work.

Abbreviations:

MNCN Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Madrid

MNHN Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris

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RESULTS

Family RISSOIDAE Gray, 1847

Genus *Alvania* Risso, 1826

Alvania gascoignei spec. nov.

Type material: Holotype (Fig. 1) and 1 paratype in the MNCN; one paratype (Fig. 2) in MNHN; six more in CER. All from type locality.

Other material examined: 1 shell, 4 juveniles and 16 fragments.

Etymology: The specific name is after Angus Gascoigne, an English naturalist living in São Tomé, who participated and played an important role in the organization of the Annobón 2000 Expedition.

Type locality: San Antonio de Palé, Annobón, Guinea Equatorial. Obtained in sediment from 10-15 m depth.

Description: Shell (Figs. 1, 2) moderately solid, ovate-conical, dirty white in colour. Protoconch (Fig. 3) somewhat more than 1 convex whorl, sculptured by seven irregularly undulating fine spiral threads. Teleoconch of about 4 convex whorls, sculptured with axial ribs and narrower spiral cords and a well defined suture. Axial ribs almost orthocline, separated by wider interspaces, which are more evident subsuturally and almost disappear on the suture. Five spiral cords on the first whorl, 9-10 on the penultimate and about 18 on the last one, with approximately equal interspaces. Aperture ovoid with a continuous peristome lacking any internal tooth. The external border of the aperture is undulating due the end of the spiral cords. The microsculpture can be observed with high magnification (Figs. 4-5), showing a great quantity of small pits on the spiral cords and 4-7 spiral nodulous fillets in the interspaces. Umbilicus absent.

Dimensions: the holotype is 2.7 x 1.5 mm.

Distribution: Only known from the type locality.

Discussion: *Alvania gascoignei* spec. nov. is different from most of the European and West African species because of its nume-

rous spiral cords. Related species with similar profile and a protoconch with a similar sculpture are, for example, *A. subsoluta* (Aradas, 1847), *A. parvula* (Jeffreys, 1884), *A. testae* (Aradas and Maggiore, 1884), *A. tomentosa* (Pallary in Monterosato, 1920) and *A. imperspicua* (Pallary in Monterosato, 1920) (in the Mediterranean) and *A. africana* Gofas, 1999, *A. coseli* Gofas, 1999, (in West Africa). Other species of the genus have a quite similar number of spiral cords, but are different in profile and protoconch, as *A. beanii* (Hanley in Thorpe, 1844), *A. lactea* (Michaud, 1832), *A. punctura* (Montagu, 1803), *A. regina* Gofas, 1999, or *A. zylensis* Gofas and Warén, 1982.

Due to its high number of spiral cords, *A. gascoignei* spec. nov. shows affinity to some species of the genus *Onoba* H. and A. Adams, 1852, but its sculpture is more prominent and the external enlargement of the aperture is different from that of most of the species of this genus. In the other hand, this species shows affinity with the genus *Manzonina* Brusina, 1870 in some characters (shape and microsculpture).

This species has not been found in the many samples made by several collectors on the island of São Tomé. Thus, it can provisionally be considered to be endemic to the island of Annobon.

(Right page) Figures 1-5. *Alvania gascoignei* spec. nov. 1: holotype, 2.7 mm, San Antonio de Palé, Annobon (MNCN); 2: paratype, 2.7 mm, Annobon (MNHN); 3: protoconch, paratype (MNCN); 4, 5: microsculpture of the holotype.

(Página derecha) Figuras 1-5. *Alvania gascoignei* spec. nov. 1: holotipo, 2,7 mm, San Antonio de Palé, Annobon (MNCN); 2: paratipo, 2,7 mm, Annobon (MNHN); 3: protoconcha, paratipo (MNCN); 4, 5: microescultura del holotipo.

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